

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERVIEWING IN TEACHING AND LEARNING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Umarkhodjayeva Dilnoza Mirzakirovna

teacher,

The department of "Languages " of Tashkent
state agrarian university Tashkent,Uzbekistan,
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Annotation

The aim of this article is to show interviewing effectively is a difficult skill requiring much practice, especially when used as rigorous research instrument. This task, however, presents the informal interview as an accessible data collection method for busy teachers by helping them to use the interview in combination with other methods. There are practical reasons why we suggest combining methods in this way.

Key words

Teacher/learner , participants ,interview, the informal interview, technical issues, new challenge of interviewing, record the interview, combining methods

Аннотация

Цель данной статьи - показать эффективное собеседование - сложный навык, требующий большой практики, особенно когда он используется в качестве строгого инструмента исследования. Эта задача, однако, представляет неформальное интервью как доступный метод сбора данных для занятых учителей, помогая им использовать интервью в сочетании с другими методами. Есть практические причины, по которым мы предлагаем комбинировать методы таким образом.

Ключевые слова

Учитель / ученик, участники, интервью, неформальное интервью, технические вопросы, новая задача собеседования, запись интервью, методы комбинирования

Izoh

Ushbu ilmiy maqolada ko'zda tutilgan mavzu shu haqdaki, samarali intervyu berish juda ko'p tajribani talab qiladigan qiyin mahoratdir, ayniqsa jiddiy tadqiqot vositasi sifatida ishlatilganda. Biroq, bu vazifa norasmiy intervyuni band bo'lgan o'qituvchilar uchun boshqa usullar bilan birgalikda foydalanishga yordam berish orqali ma'lumotlarni yig'ish uchun qulay usul sifatida taqdim etadi. Usullarni shu tarzda birlashtirishni taklif qilishimizning amaliy sabablari bor.

Kalit so'zlar

O'qituvchi/o'quvchi, ishtirokchilar, intervyu, norasmiy intervyu, texnik muammolar, intervyuning vazifasi, suhbatni yozib olish, usullarni birlashtirish

Of course, interviewing effectively is a difficult skill requiring much practice, especially when used as rigorous research instrument. The time and the date of the interview must be fixed beforehand. The interview should be very beneficial if it is recorded. After this ceremony, we can discuss about what we have learnt according to the interview. The same time every participant can follow his or her own reflection on video. They can easily find themselves comfortably and uncomfortably while watching and

analyzing their interview. In the end teachers, learners must be thanked for their giving information and sharing some problems with the participants. One way of finding out about learners' and teachers' opinions is to ask them to respond to a questionnaire. Teachers can consult classes of learners of their choice about the topic selected by writing a brief questionnaire in small groups, giving it to the learners, and then presenting and evaluating the resulting data in a future training session. It will be very fruitful, if teachers or learners can lead a brief general discussion, focusing on the topic. Teachers must pay particular attention to the clarity of aims of each questionnaire.

The procedure of the interview takes an hour or so. Structured interview are defined beforehand. It must be a very tight structure; the questions should be very understandable to answer. They will be used orally. The topic must be clear and useful for educational process. The interview should be brief and it is interviewed during a class or at other times. The interview could be conducted in the learner's mother tongue, especially when a learner may experience even more difficulty thoughts and feelings in English than in his or her own language. But nowadays everybody tries to learn English. That's why we can interview in English. We can also record the interview if possible. The interviewed information may be demonstrated to learners or teachers.

Learners, sometimes, teachers also are very shy to take a microphone before camera. But time by time we should teach them to be very confident and self-esteem to express their ideas, opinions, and their point of view. Every interview has to think of a way of summing up at the end. Speech of the presenter must be slow and understandable. We can use different types of visual aids such as the blackboard, projector, phonographs, posters, etc., which will help you to bring your work to life. In the conclusion section we would like to comment on the advantages and beneficial sides of interviewing. Also we want to share some opinions about interviewing and presenting. Decide what to do about questions from the audience, and tell the audience about your policy at the beginning of your presentation or interview. Be always sure before presenting. Please, practice beforehand, checking your timing in particular. Below we can add much more recommendations about interviewing what to do or what not to do. You can use cards as prompts in case you forget your lines. Please practice in front of a mirror and tape record yourself. Talking a long time is not adapted, because nobody can concentrate for that long. Your speech should be brief, understandable, and clear to listen, supplying very useful information. Please, vary sound of your voice, the position of your body and mind your body-language. For each presentation, interview please, pick out and discuss what was effective about it. It is the best way to share and compare ideas with those of your trainer and other participants, and discuss.

There are a lot of advantages for teachers and also learners. It helps both teachers and learners to prepare and evaluate an informal interview and develop teachers' and learners' interviewing skills.

Topic and aims interview must be chosen according to learners or teachers interest. We should name our interview and show the reason why we have chosen this one. The time and the date of the interview must be fixed beforehand. The interview should be very beneficial if it is recorded. After this ceremony, we can discuss about what we have learnt according to the interview. The same time every participant can follow his or her own reflection on video. They can easily find themselves comfortably and uncomfortably while

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Hopkins suggests the following advantages for the teacher/learner interview: the teacher is in direct contact with the learner; the learner is familiar with the teacher, and more at ease; the teacher is able to seek the desired information directly and not through a ream of irrelevant information; an interview can be held in lesson time or outside the class; problems with the interview can be followed up immediately when they arise. On the hand, the advantages he identifies include that: it is time-consuming; may be carried out with some kind of recording equipment, with attendant disadvantages, and it is frequently difficult to get young younger children to explain their thoughts and feelings.

This task, however, presents the informal interview as an accessible data collection method for busy teachers by helping them to use the interview in combination with other methods. There are practical reasons why we suggest combining methods in this way.

Firstly, it interviewing is time-consuming, teachers may use a previously administered questionnaires as a basis for their interviewing schedule.

Secondly, many of the technical issues related to interviewing which is important to get right in order for it to be effective are also relevant to questionnaires, including having a clear aim, ethical considerations, the length and layout, the language to be used, the response method, etc. so teachers can transfer their experience of using questionnaires to the new challenge of interviewing.

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useful information. Please, vary sound of your voice, the position of your body and mind your body-language. For each presentation, interview please, pick out and discuss what was effective about it. It is the best way to share and compare ideas with those of your trainer and other participants, and discuss. In our teaching period we, as teachers are often interviewed by our colleagues and learners. We are very grateful about this process.

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